

Kinetics and mechanism of the reaction of hydroxopenta-aquarhodium(III) ion with L-proline in aqueous solution

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Abstract : The kinetics of the reaction of L-proline (H_2L^+) with hydroxopenta-aquarhodium(III) has been studied over the range $2.48 \leq 10^3 [\text{H}_2\text{L}^+] \leq 7.44$, $3.5 \leq \text{pH} \leq 4.5$, $50^\circ \leq t \leq 70^\circ$ at $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO_4). The reaction proceeds through an outersphere association between $[\text{Rh}(\text{OH})]^{2+}$ and HL (conjugate base of H_2L^+) followed by transformation of the outer into an inner sphere complex (chelate is formed) by slow interchange. The anation rate constant k_{an} of RhOH^{2+} at 25°C and $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO_4) is estimated to be $1.56 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger for k_{an} path are found to be $54.5 \pm 3.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $-135.7 \pm 10.5 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. The product of the reaction has been isolated and characterised. The substitution reaction follows an Ia path.

Keywords : Kinetics, rhodium(III), L-proline.

Rhodium(III) is unique in character because of its proficiency in catalytic reactions as well as in ligand substitution reactions. The mechanistic path involves dissociative interchange to associative interchange depending upon the type of the ligand¹.

The present study reveals the kinetic behaviour of L-proline as an anating ligand towards hydroxopenta-aquarhodium(III) cation. The substituted product has been isolated and characterised.

Results and discussion

Effect of $[\text{Rh}^{3+}]$ on reaction rate : The pseudo-first order plots were linear ($r = 0.99$) in each case with varying amount of complex, giving $10^4 k_{\text{obs}} = (6.4 \pm 0.2) \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 55°C with $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\text{pH} = 4.5$. The reaction is first order dependent on complex concentration.

At 55°C , $[\text{Rh}^{3+}]_{\text{T}} = 4.93 \times 10^{-4}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{L}^+]_{\text{T}} = 3.70 \times 10^{-3}$ and $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO_4), when the pH was varied from 3.5 to 4.5, $10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ were found to increase from 3.5 to 5.33 s^{-1} . At $\text{pH} = 3.5, 4.0, 4.3, 4.5$ the values of $10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ are 4.5, 4.83, 5.07 and 5.33 s^{-1} . Solution of L-proline acts as buffer. The increase in observed rate with pH may be due to increase in the concentration of $[\text{Rh}(\text{OH})]^{2+}$ and [HL]. Dissociation of $[\text{Rh}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ may be given as.

The $\text{p}K_{\text{h}(1)}$, $\text{p}K_{\text{h}(2)}$ values of $[\text{Rh}(\text{OH}_2)_6]^{3+}$ are 3.6 and 4.7 respectively at 25°C . With increase in pH the percentage of the more labile hydroxopenta-aquarhodium(III) species increases. The hydroxide ligand increases the water exchange rate constant of $[\text{Rh}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}$ relative to $[\text{Rh}(\text{OH}_2)_6]^{3+}$. L-Proline also participates in acid-base reaction equilibria. $\text{p}K_1$ and $\text{p}K_2$ of L-proline³ are 1.9 ± 0.1 and 10.38 ± 0.03 respectively at ionic strength 0.1 mol dm^{-3} at 25°C . The correct pH chosen in the present study is 3.5 to 4.5 where the active species involved in the reaction is HL. At pH higher than 4.5 precipitation of Rh^{3+} takes place. The effect of pH can be explained by eq. (3).

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_1 + k_2 K_{\text{h}(1)} [\text{H}^+]^{-1} \quad (3)$$

Here k_1 and k_2 are the observed rate constants when $[\text{Rh}(\text{OH}_2)_6]^{3+}$ and $[\text{Rh}(\text{OH}_2)_5\text{OH}]^{2+}$ are the reacting species respectively. The plot of k_{obs} (55°C) vs $[\text{H}^+]^{-1}$ was linear with intercept = 5×10^{-4} and slope = 2×10^{-9} . The value of correlation coefficient was found to be 0.9941.

k_{obs} increases in a nonlinear fashion with increase in $[\text{H}_2\text{L}^+]_{\text{T}}$ indicating outersphere complexation between the reactant species (Table 1). The reaction mechanism is similar to the work reported earlier¹.

The plot of k_{obs}^{-1} versus $[\text{HL}]_{\text{T}}^{-1}$ should be linear with an intercept = k_{an}^{-1} and slope = $(k_{\text{an}} K_{\text{M}})^{-1}$. This plot was linear at all experimental temperatures studied. k_{an} was determined from the reciprocal of the intercept and K_{M} calculated from intercept/slope ratio. The values of k_{an} , K_{M} are collected in Table 1.

Table 1. Values of $10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s^{-1}) at different $[\text{H}_2\text{L}^+]$ and at different temperatures

$[\text{Rh}^{3+}]_{\text{T}} = 4.93 \times 10^{-4}$, $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO_4), $\text{pH} = 4.5$				
$10^3 [\text{HL}]$	Temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)			
(mol dm^{-3})	50 $^{\circ}$	55 $^{\circ}$	60 $^{\circ}$	70 $^{\circ}$
2.48	2.77 (2.70)	4.33 (4.27)	5.67 (5.53)	11.24 (11.06)
3.70	3.42 (3.49)	5.33 (5.47)	6.83 (7.03)	13.55 (11.06)
4.96	3.82 (4.11)	6.33 (6.40)	7.67 (8.19)	15.63 (16.10)
6.10	4.73 (4.55)	7.17 (7.06)	9.5 (9.0)	18.70 (17.70)
7.44	5.3 (4.98)	7.83 (7.63)	10.17 (9.76)	19.18 (19.12)
$10^3 k_{\text{an}}/\text{s}^{-1}$	0.86	1.28	1.58	3.01
K_{M}	185.05	202.08	217.29	234.38

Data in the parenthesis are for k_{calcd} .

The reactions were studied at four different temperatures with different ligand concentrations. Activation parameters were calculated using Eyring equation and compared with literature data of analogous systems. The low ΔH^{\ddagger} value compared with the aqua exchange process⁴ together with highly negative ΔS^{\ddagger} value suggest an associative mechanism for the substitution reaction. $k_{\text{an}}(25^{\circ}) = 1.54 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ which is found to be greater than $k_{\text{ex}}(25^{\circ}) = 1.99 \times 10^{-9} \text{ s}^{-1}$ also supports the above proposition⁵. The value of ΔH^{\ddagger} and ΔS^{\ddagger} are $54.5 \pm 3.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $-137.7 \pm 10.5 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. ΔH° and ΔS° values were calculated from the $\ln K_{\text{M}}$ versus T^{-1} plot⁶. ΔH° was calculated from the slope and ΔS° from the intercept with $r = 0.996$. ΔH° and ΔS° values were found to be $10.57 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $76.19 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. ΔG° value for the anation reaction was calculated from the value of ΔH° and ΔS° and was found to be $-12.13 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. Negative value of ΔG° is in support of spontaneous formation of an outersphere association complex.

The isokinetic plot stands as the testimony for the fact that, the same type of mechanism was followed for analogous substitution reactions involving various amino acids.

Characterisation of product complex :

A mixture of $[\text{Rh}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6](\text{ClO}_4)_3$ and L-proline in a molar proportion 1 : 1 was prepared. The solution was heated on a water bath and left overnight at room temperature, when the product complex separated out. It was purified by recrystallization.

IR spectra were taken in a Shimadzu FTIR 8000 spectrophotometer. Most of the peaks of L-proline in the substituted product retain its identity. The infrared frequencies associated with carboxylato proton of the substituted product appearing at 1550 cm^{-1} (s) and 1340 cm^{-1} (w) with 75 cm^{-1} and 70 cm^{-1} downshift from 1625 cm^{-1} and 1410 cm^{-1} respectively indicate the co-ordination of carboxylato group to Rh^{3+} ion, through 'O' atom. The infrared frequencies associated with N-H proton of the substituted product appearing at 1520 cm^{-1} with a 45 cm^{-1} downshift from 1565 cm^{-1} (NH_2^+ stretching frequency of pure L-proline)⁷ indicate co-ordination of 'N' to Rh^{3+} . 3674 cm^{-1} and 3649 cm^{-1} ν_{str} (O-H) of the aqua Rh^{3+} complex have been retained which is an indication of presence of co-ordinated water. $\nu_{\text{def}}(\text{O-H})$ at 1699 cm^{-1} is an indication of the presence of co-ordinated water in the product complex⁸. From the individual assignment of different bands it can be presumed that the substituted species is a monochelate.

Experimental

The complex $[\text{Rh}(\text{OH}_2)_6](\text{ClO}_4)_3$ was prepared according to the published method⁹. The chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Doubly distilled water was used to prepare all the kinetic solutions. The complex was characterised spectrally and by elemental analysis. Kinetics was carried out at $\text{pH} = 4.5$, where the complex species exists as $[\text{Rh}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5(\text{OH})]^{2+}$.

The absorbance measurements for kinetic studies were done using CECIL CE 7200 UV-Vis scanning spectrophotometer equipped with CE 2024 thermoelectric controller. Reaction progress was monitored at 440 nm, pseudo-first order conditions were maintained throughout the runs by using a large (\geq five fold) excess of L-proline.

Rhodium(III) complex and L-proline in the ratio 1 : 2, 1 : 4, 1 : 8 and 1 : 10 was theromostated for 12 h at 60°C . Absorbance of the experimental solution containing aquarhodium(III) ion and L-proline increases with time

and ultimately arriving at a constant value (Fig. 1). The composition of the complex formed as determined by Job's method was found to be 1 : 1 (metal : ligand). The pH of the solution was adjusted and measurements were carried out on Elico digital pH meter with an accuracy of ± 0.01 .

Fig. 1. Repetitive spectral scan of the Rh^{III} and L-proline mixture : (1) $[\text{Rh}^{\text{III}}] = 2.47 \times 10^{-4}$, $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO_4), $\text{pH} = 4.5$ at 50°C , (2) $[\text{Rh}^{\text{III}}] = 2.47 \times 10^{-4}$, $[\text{L-proline}]_{\text{T}} = 2.47 \times 10^{-3}$, $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO_4), $\text{pH} = 4.5$ at 50°C and at 0 min, (3) at 15 min, (4) at 45 min, (5) at 60 min, (6) at 75 min.

The rate constants k_{obs} were evaluated by the plots of $\ln(A_{\infty} - A_t)$ vs t , where A_{∞} and A_t are the absorbances at equilibrium and at time ' t ' respectively. The rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The correlation coefficient of plots used to determine k_{obs} and k_{calcd} values were found to be 0.99 in most of the cases. There is a good agreement between the k_{obs} and k_{calcd} values.

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